

Development of an ICP-AES technique for the determination of nickel content in blast furnace inputs

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Abstract : The importance of nickel in the steel industry is significant due to a wide variety of applications as an alloying component in stainless steel. In this context, the present paper endeavors to determine the nickel content of different blast furnace (BF) inputs such as iron ore, coal, coke and sinter. This has been done by analyzing the different raw materials using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES) technique. The ICP-AES technique was chosen because it was observed that as the content of nickel was very low in these raw materials, it would be difficult to analyze the same using classical methods such as the dimethylglyoxime (gravimetric) method. The major objective of the present study was to deliver an accurate and less-time consuming method based on an instrumental technique, namely, the ICP-AES technique for analysis of nickel (low content) in different blast furnace inputs. In this context, the established method was validated by the evaluation of certified reference materials (CRMs) namely ECRM 681-1 and ECRM 679-1 and thus, it was felt that the present method was very much appropriate for determination of nickel content below 0.01%.

Keywords : Nickel, ICP-AES analysis, blast furnace inputs, validation.

Introduction

Stainless steel containing high percentage of nickel has been useful in many demanding applications such as gas turbines and chemical plants. The role of nickel, particularly, in preparation of different grades of stainless steel is highly significant which can be understood from the following facts. A small addition of nickel in low alloyed ferritic stainless steel provides favourable properties such as grain size control and increasing the yield strength. Also, it is the one element which controls the amount of Cr to be added, which is necessary for austenite phase formation at higher temperatures and is a prerequisite for martensite formation upon quenching. Also, it increases the corrosion resistance of the martensitic grades to both general and localized corrosion. Similarly, it also gives higher corrosion resistance (general, localized and stress corrosion cracking) to the PH grades, where it is needed for obtaining the austenite to martensite transformation¹.

In view of the above discussion, the significance of nickel can be clearly understood in the iron and steel

industry. In this context, the present paper endeavors to determine the nickel content of different blast furnace (BF) inputs such as iron ore, coal, coke and sinter. The analysis of nickel in steel has been described in standard test methods such as IS : 228 (Part 5)² and ASTM E 1473-09³ and is based on the classical dimethylglyoxime (gravimetric) method. However, these methods are beset with the limitation that the nickel content in the sample should be $\leq 0.1\%$ m/m. Thus, the classical method will be not be suitable for determination of nickel in various BF inputs as the nickel content is below 0.01% in these materials. Therefore, alternative methods based on instrumental techniques have to be established in this case. In this context, it was observed that IS : 1448 (P : 145) describes an atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) based method for analysis of low-content nickel in petroleum products⁴. Thus, it was felt that the analysis of low-content nickel can be done by using Inductively Coupled Plasma (ICP-AES) technique for improved accuracy. The ICP-AES technique was therefore chosen as the analytical method in the present work and the details of the work including

validation of the method are described in the subsequent sections of this paper.

Principle of the ICP-AES spectrometer :

Methodology of measurement of analyte :

A typical schematic diagram presenting the major components and layout of a typical ICP spectrometer is shown in Fig. 1⁵. In ICP-AES technique, the sample is transported to the spectrometer as a liquid sample after a suitable method of digestion/extraction of the solid sample

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram presenting the major components and layout of a typical ICP-AES spectrometer.

into the liquid form. The liquid sample is then converted into an aerosol inside the spectrometer by a process known as nebulization wherein a component known as a nebulizer is used. The sample aerosol is then taken to the high temperature plasma, wherein it is desolvated, vaporized, atomized and ionized by the plasma. In this process, the excited atoms and ions emit radiation which is characteristic of each element. This emitted radiation is then collected by a suitable device such as photo-multiplier tube (PMT) or advanced detector systems such as charge-injection device (CID) or a charge-coupled device (CCD) which is connected to a computer via the data acquisition software. Thus, qualitative information about the injected sample is obtained.

Quantitative information for the injected sample is also obtained by the data acquisition software by means of analysis of a plot between emission intensity (measured in counts per second) versus concentration of different calibration solutions (of known concentration) for the particular analyte, which are introduced in the ICP during the creation of method for analysis of the particular

analyte. A calibration curve is plotted for the analyte and the emission intensity of the analyte is checked with respect to this calibration curve for determination of the corresponding concentration of the analyte. Such calibration curves are usually linear over four to six orders of magnitude in ICP-OES, thus giving this technique the advantage of higher accuracy as compared to arc and spark sources, wherein there is non-linearity in the calibration plots leading to increased number of calibration solutions per analyte⁵.

Some important components of the spectrometer :

After having a brief overview of the methodology of the measurement, it would be appropriate to understand the functions of some important components of the spectrometer, such as the one-piece torch and cross-flow nebulizer.

One-piece torch :

The one-piece torch is one of the vital components of the ICP spectrometer which holds the plasma generated by the radio-frequency (RF) generator which provides the power (about 700–1500 Watts) to generate and sustain the plasma. A schematic of the one-piece torch is given in Fig. 2⁵. From the figure, it can be observed that the torch consists of three concentric quartz tubes for argon flow and injection of the sample aerosol. There is a narrow space between the two outer tubes so that the

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of one-piece torch used in ICP-AES.

argon gas emerges at a high velocity. The function of this emerging argon flow is to cool the quartz walls of torch (to prevent melting of the torch) during the presence of high-temperature plasma, and is therefore known as the 'plasma flow' or the 'coolant flow' and is normally about 7–15 liters per minute.

The chamber between the outer and inner tube also sends argon gas, designated as the 'auxiliary flow' which supports the sample aerosol introduction into the plasma by keeping the plasma discharge away from the injector tube and the intermediate tube. Also, in case of organic analytes, the auxiliary flow is useful in reducing the carbon formation at the tip of the injector tube. This flow is around 1 liter per minute. Finally, the argon gas flow that is responsible for carrying the sample aerosol to the plasma is designated as the 'sample' or 'nebulizer flow'. Due to the small diameter of the injector tube, the velocity of the sample flow is such that at even a low flow rate of 1 liter per minute, it has the potential to punch a hole through the plasma. Thus, the torch is a very vital component of the spectrometer.

Nebulizer :

A nebulizer is a device that converts the liquid sample in the form of an aerosol which is transported to the plasma, wherein it is desolvated, vaporized, atomized and ionized by the plasma. There are different types of nebulizers such as the Meinhard nebulizer, the Babington nebulizer, the V-groove nebulizer, the Conespray nebulizer and the Cross-flow nebulizer. As the cross-flow nebulizer is used in the present work, it is herewith briefly described. The action of this nebulizer may be compared with that of a perfume atomizer. In this nebulizer, the high speed flow of argon is directed perpendicular to the capillary tube, wherein the gas flow is parallel in case of the concentric nebulizers. Aerosol generation takes place when the contact between the high speed argon and the liquid (through the peristaltic pump) causes the liquid to break up into an aerosol. One of the advantages of this type of nebulizer is that it is chemically resistant to different samples as it is contained in a polyetheretherketone (PEEK) body. Also, these nebulizers are usually more rugged and corrosion-resistant than the glass concentric nebulizers. A schematic of the nebulizer is as shown in Fig. 3⁵.

Experimental

Reagents, glassware and other apparatus required :

Concentrated hydrochloric acid, perchloric acid and hydrofluoric acid solution (40%) were procured from E. Merck, India. 100 mL Teflon beakers, hot plate, 10 mL measuring cylinder, 100 mL volumetric flasks, glass fun-

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of a cross-flow nebulizer.

nels were used during the preparation of the sample. The analysis of the prepared samples was done by using an ICP-spectrometer (Make : SPECTRO-ARCOS). In this instrument, the cross-flow nebulizer has been used. Double distilled water confirming to Type II of ASTM D 1193-06⁶ was used in the preparation of the reagent solutions.

Nature of samples :

The details of the samples have been presented in Table 1. From the table, it can be observed that the samples were essentially iron ore, sinter, coal and coke samples taken from different locations in Tata Steel. These materials are the basic inputs of the blast furnace.

Sl. no.	Sample identity	Nature of sample
1.	Joda fine/CRMT/6193/11	Iron ore
2.	SP#2/SN/B1	Sinter
3.	B/o fine/CRMT/6192/11	Iron ore
4.	SP1/SN/A/6-4-11	Sinter
5.	SP#3 Sinter A-2	Sinter
6.	SP#4 Sinter A-2	Sinter
7.	CP2/Coke/A1/2.4.11	Coke
8.	West Bokaro Coal	Coal
9.	Jamadoba Coal	Coal
10.	CP1/Coke/A1/2.4.11	Coke
11.	HBF Coke	Coke

Procedure for sample preparation :

The following sample preparation procedure was adopted. 1 g of sample was carefully weighed and placed in a Teflon beaker. 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid solution was prepared and 25 mL of this solution was added to the sample. This was then followed by adding 10 mL of perchloric acid. The solution was then subjected to slow heating on the hot plate. After the content of the beaker

reduced to almost half, 20 mL of hydrofluoric solution (40%) was added and the heating was continued till complete dryness was achieved.

The contents of the beaker were then allowed to come to room temperature and then 20 mL of 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid solution was added for dissolving the dried mass. The resultant solution was then transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with distilled water. The solutions were then analyzed by the ICP spectrometer. The analysis was done in duplicate for ensuring the repeatability of the analysis.

To perform the validation of the method, solutions of two certified reference material (CRM) were also prepared and analyzed as described for the test samples. The analyzed CRMs were ECRM 681-1 and ECRM 679-1.

Creation of method in ICP :

A new method was created to determine the content of nickel in the various blast furnace inputs. Table 2 presents the measuring conditions for this new method. Argon was chosen as the monitoring line at a wavelength of 430.01 nm whereas nickel was evaluated as the analyte at wavelength, 231.604 nm respectively. The other measuring conditions can be observed from Table 2.

Table 2. ICP operating conditions of method for determination of nickel

Sl. no.	Operating parameters	Value
1.	Power (Watt)	1400
2.	Nebulizer	Cross-flow
3.	Spray chamber	Double-pass Scott type
4.	Coolant flow (L/min)	14.00
5.	Auxiliary flow (L/min)	1.00
6.	Nebulizer flow (L/min)	0.95
7.	Wavelength for Ni (nm)	231.604
8.	Integration time (s)	28
9.	Plasma stabilization time (min)	30
10.	No. of measurements	2

Analysis procedure :

The analysis of the prepared samples was done by using an ICP-spectrometer (Make : SPECTRO-ARCOS). A new method was created to analyze these samples. For the purpose of calibrating the method, five calibration standard solutions were prepared. These five calibration standards consisted of 0, 1, 10, 50 and 100 ppm solutions of nickel and were prepared from 100 ppm and 1000 ppm

stock solutions of nickel respectively. 10 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to all the calibration solutions for maintaining the matrix effect. The calibration solutions were then run in the spectrometer so as to obtain a calibration curve. After the calibration, it was observed that the co-relation coefficient for the linear calibration plot was 0.99985.

Results and discussion

Validation of method :

To perform the validation of the method, solutions of two certified reference material (CRM) standards were prepared and analyzed as described for the test samples. The analysis was carried out in duplicate. The analyzed CRMs were ECRM 681-1 and ECRM 679-1. The analyzed results of the CRMs are given in Table 3. It can be observed from the table, that the observed and certified values in case of all the CRMs are in agreement, thus validating the method.

Sample analysis :

The sample solutions prepared were analyzed using the new developed method in the ICP instrument. The results of the analysis (carried out in duplicate) are presented below in Table 4 wherein it can be observed that the nickel content is basically of a low order (<0.01%) in all the samples. It can be also observed from the duplicate values that the analysis is repeatable in nature.

Table 3. Validation of method by analysis of certified reference materials

Sl. No.	CRM id	Certified value of nickel in certified reference material (%)	Observed value of nickel in certified reference material (%)	
			Value 1	Value 2
1.	ECRM 681-1	0.016 ± 0.001	0.018	0.018
2.	ECRM 679-1	0.0095 ± 0.0014	0.0125	0.0123

Table 4. Observed values for analyzed samples

Sl. No.	Sample id	Observed value of nickel (%)	
		Value 1	Value 2
1.	Joda fine/CRMT/6193/11	0.0068	0.0066
2.	SP#2/SN/B1	0.0094	0.0096
3.	B/o fine/CRMT/6192/11	0.0049	0.0052
4.	SP1/SN/A/6-4-11	0.0096	0.0097

Table-4 (contd.)

5.	SP#3 Sinter A-2	0.0079	0.0079
6.	SP#4 Sinter A-2	0.0077	0.0075
7.	CP2/Coke/A1/2.4.11	0.0062	0.0069
8.	West Bokaro Coal	0.0072	0.0066
9.	Jamadoba Coal	0.0071	0.0070
10.	CP1/Coke/A1/2.4.11	0.0074	0.0072
11.	HBF Coke	0.0067	0.0074

Conclusion

A new method was created for estimation of nickel in various blast furnace input samples. The method was validated by the evaluation of CRMs namely ECRM 681-1 and ECRM 679-1. It was observed that the observed and certified values in case of both the CRMs were in agreement, thus validating the method for analysis of nickel in the different blast furnace inputs for low-nickel content ($\leq 0.01\%$).

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